

The MPA Europe online atlas for marine spatial planning

Deliverable 5.7

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 5.7 overview

This report introduces the online atlas of prioritisation layers and environmental context developed as part of the [MPA Europe project](#). The atlas provides spatial information that can support marine spatial planning professionals and other stakeholders, both for straightforward consultation and for analyses related to marine protected area designation, pressure impacts on marine ecosystems, and more.

Background

Supporting broader Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) involves providing data and tools to practitioners and stakeholders which enable them to efficiently design Marine Protected Areas (MPA) and manage the use of our seas and oceans based on data-driven recommendations. Atlases are collections of maps that contain geographical information and can be displayed as interactive web-based user interfaces. They are commonly used to assist people in understanding geographic relationships related to, for example, environmental concerns (e.g., contaminants), human activities (e.g., shipping), management policies and so inform MSP in specific regions. Examples include the (1) [European Atlas of the Seas](#), a well-established continental scale atlas providing information about Europe's marine environment, and covering several topics including climate change, biodiversity, seabed habitats, aquaculture, fisheries, tourism, employment, population, security, energy, transport and shipping, pollution and litter, oceanographic monitoring and nutrients (Barale et al., 2015); (2) [Atlas of Biodiversity Conservation in the Coral Triangle](#), a regional atlas including three web applications or spatial layers: biodiversity features (e.g., endemic species), areas of importance for biodiversity conservation (e.g., MPA), and optimal areas to expand the MPA network (Asaad et al., 2019); (3) [Priority Areas for Marine Biodiversity Conservation](#), a global atlas that contains twenty-six layers, including four biome layers (seagrass, kelp, mangrove and shallow-water coral reefs), environmental data (e.g., rugosity, sea surface temperature), biodiversity data (e.g., species endemism, species richness), and seven ecosystem classes developed by Zhao et al., (2020). The MPA Europe project atlas will similarly enable readers to turn on and off different map layers so they can see the spatial relationships between, for example, the areas prioritised for 10 % protection, with environmental features.

Atlas

The online atlas for marine spatial planning (*AtlasForMSP* hereafter) is available on the [MPA Europe map platform](#) (OBIS, 2024) hosted by the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) (Figure 1). It is a compilation of geospatial files (in raster format, Table 1) for the MPA Europe study area at a spatial resolution of 0.05 degrees latitude-longitude. The atlas layers are grouped into (a) the areas prioritised for protection, called Representative Biodiversity Areas (RBA), using systematic conservation planning analysis, (b) species and habitats (Principe et al., 2023ab; OBIS, 2024), (c) seabed organic carbon stores (Lønborg et al., submitted), (d) MSP information, and (d) environmental data (Assis et al., 2018, 2023; Burrows et al., 2023)

The Prioritisation layers comprise*:

1. PRIORITISATION FOR BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION-RBA for all European marine species based on the current distribution and projected species distribution shifts under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway SSP5 climate emissions scenario by end-of-century (2100) of 10,038 marine species.
2. PRIORITISATION - TOP 10% RBAS for all European marine species based on current and projected distribution of 10,038 taxa.
3. PRIORITISATION - TOP 30% RBAS for all European marine species based on current and projected distribution of 10,038 taxa.
4. PRIORITISATION - TOP 50% RBAS for all European marine species based on current and projected distribution of 10,038 taxa.
5. PRIORITY AREAS FOR COMMERCIAL FISH - RBAS for commercial fish species based on the current distribution of 661 commercially important fish species.
6. PRIORITY AREAS - TOP 10% RBAS for commercial fish species based on the current distribution of 661 commercially important fish species.

7. PRIORITY AREAS - TOP 30% RBAS for commercial fish species based on the current distribution of 661 commercially important fish species.
8. PRIORITY AREAS - TOP 50% RBAS for commercial fish species based on the current distribution of 661 commercially important fish species.

The MSP layers comprise:

9. MPA EUROPE MARINE REGIONS: the four European marine regions of North-East Atlantic Ocean, and adjacent Baltic, Black and Mediterranean seas.
10. MARINE PROTECTED AREAS - LEVEL PROTECTION: MPAs classified by level of protection following Aminan-Biquet et al., (2024), Sim (2025) and Eskuche-Keith et al (in prep).*

The Species and Habitats comprise:

11. SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELS (SDMs): current and projected distributions of 12,039 marine species. The projected species distribution shifts under five Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP1-5) by two future time periods: mid-century (2050) and end-of-century (2100).
12. HABITAT-FORMING SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELS: current and projected distributions of species that form significant habitats for other species with their projected distributions under five Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP1-5) by mid-century (2050) and end-of-century (2100):
 - a. seagrasses *Posidonia oceanica*, *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Zostera noltii* and *Zostera marina*;
 - b. kelps *Laminaria hyperborea*, *L. ochroleuca*, *Saccharina latissima* (syn *L. saccharina*), and *Saccorhiza polyschides*;
 - c. bivalves *Mytilus edulis*, *M. galloprovincialis*, *Modiolus modiolus*, and *Ostrea edulis*;
 - d. maerl *Lithothamnion corallioides*, *L. glaciale*, and *Phymatolithon calcareum*;
 - e. polychaetes *Sabellaria alveolata* and *S. spinulosa*;
 - f. corals *Desmophyllum pertusum*, *Madrepora oculata*, and *Solenosmilia variabilis*.
13. BIOGENIC HABITAT DISTRIBUTION MODELS: current and projected distribution of six biogenic habitat groups by stacking species distribution maps (sSDM) of the respective species:
 - g. seagrass meadows;
 - h. kelp forests;
 - i. bivalve beds;
 - j. maerl beds;
 - k. polychaete reefs;
 - l. and coral reefs.
14. EUSEAMAP (2023) HABITAT TYPES*: distribution of selected marine habitats from EMODnet Seabed habitats. The broad-scale seabed habitat map across the MPA Europe study area are organised based on the EUNIS 2007/full-detail classification.

The Blue Carbon layers comprise:

15. OC IN MARINE SEDIMENTS (EURO_CARBOIN): concentrations of organic carbon (OC) in seabed sediment samples from the “EURO-CARBON” dataset.
16. OC IN MARINE SEDIMENTS (MODEL): A modeled map of organic carbon in marine sediments of the European seas.**

The Physical Environmental layers comprise:

17. BATHYMETRY (m): water depth above the seabed.
18. TERRAIN RUGGEDNESS, TOPOGRAPHIC HETEROGENEITY, OR RUGOSITY (unitless): the difference in depth between adjacent cells of the seabed. It indicates seabed habitat complexity.

19. SEAFLOOR GEOMORPHIC FEATURES (unitless): manually named geomorphological features that characterize the seafloor (e.g., abyssal, basins, canyons, escarpments, glacial throughs, ridges, shelves and slopes).
20. SEABED SLOPE (unitless): the depth changes over distance indicating the inclination or gradient of the seabed.
21. WAVE FETCH (WAVE EXPOSURE) (unitless): measurement of the wave exposure based on the distance over water that the wind blows in a single direction or the area in which ocean waves are generated by the wind. Wave exposure is the sum of wave fetch (distance to the nearest land in angular sectors around locations of interest), fetch orientation (the weighted mean angle of fetch vectors) and fetch directionality (the weighted standard deviation of fetch orientation).
22. CURRENT SPEED (m s^{-1}): the speed of sea water movement.
23. RIVER RUNOFF: the discharge volume of large rivers in Europe from the HydroSHEDS database.
24. DISTANCE TO COAST (km): distance of any point in the sea to the nearest coastline at intervals of 0.05 degrees.

The Temperature and Chemical Environmental layers comprise:

25. SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE (SST) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): the temperature of the seawater at the surface, usually with the first 5 mm depth.
26. SEA BOTTOM TEMPERATURE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): the temperature of the water next to the seafloor.
27. AIR TEMPERATURE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): the temperature of the air at a height of 1.5 to 2 m above the ocean
28. SALINITY (unitless): the amount of dissolved salt in the seawater
29. pH (unitless): the concentration of hydrogen ions (H^+) in seawater.
30. OXYGEN CONCENTRATION (mmole m^{-3}): the amount of dissolved molecular oxygen in seawater.
31. SEA ICE COVER (percentage): the depth of sea ice on the seawater.
32. PHYTOPLANKTON CONCENTRATION (mmol m^{-3})
33. MIXED LAYER DEPTH (m): the depth to which the seawater is well mixed, typically until it reaches a pycnocline or thermocline.
34. NITRATE CONCENTRATION (mmole m^{-3}): the amount of dissolved inorganic oxidised nitrogen (mostly nitrate) in seawater.
35. PHOSPHATE CONCENTRATION (mmol m^{-3}): the amount of dissolved phosphate in seawater.
36. DIFFUSE ATTENUATION COEFFICIENT (K_d) (m^{-1}): a measure of how light dissipates with depth in seawater.
37. PHOTOSYNTHETICALLY AVAILABLE RADIATION (PAR): the measurement of the daily solar radiation within the 400 to 700 nm wavelength range, utilized by photosynthetic organisms during the process of photosynthesis. Unit: millimoles of light energy per square metre per day.

*Note: due to technical requirements, the RBA, MPA by level of protection, EUSeaMap Marine habitats from EMODnet Seabed Habitats layers will be available on the platform from 14 November.

** The layer of organic carbon (OC) in marine sediments of the European seas is part of a submitted manuscript and will become available after publication.

Discussion

This interactive platform will allow users to explore maps, layers, and information relevant to coastal and marine areas within the MPA Europe study area. One of the main advantages is its centralized access to diverse datasets, enabling better-informed decision-making. We encourage others to download and re-use the data. However, where we have sourced data from other locations users should

go to the original source for the latest version of those data and acknowledge its use by citing the original product. After user feedback, an updated version will be published in early 2026.

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Table 1. List of biotic and abiotic layers (in raster format with 0.05 resolution) included in the online *AtlasForMSP* version v1 based on the seven components of MPA Europe (Figure B). OC = organic carbon; MSP = Maritime Spatial Planning; RBA = Representative Biodiversity Area; *layer used to develop the species (and habitat) distribution models (SDMs); external data sources: [Bio-ORACLE](#); [EMODnet Seabed Habitats](#) (EMODnet SH); [EMODnet Geology](#) (EMODnet GEO); [HydroSHEDS](#)

Layer	Metadata	Main Source
Prioritisation		
Prioritisation for biodiversity conservation - RBAs		
Prioritisation - Top 10% RBAs		MPA Europe
Prioritisation - Top 30% RBAs		
Prioritisation - Top 50% RBAs	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at	
Priority areas for commercial fish - RBAs	0.05 resolution - original.	
Priority areas- Top 10% RBAs		MPA Europe (Abinaya et al., in press)
Priority areas- Top 30% RBAs		
Priority areas- Top 50% RBAs		
Marine spatial planning (MSP)		
MPA Europe marine regions	Shapefile (.gpkg format)	MPA Europe (Provoost et al., 2023)
Marine protected areas - level protection classification	Shapefile (.gpkg format)	Eskuche-Keith et al (in prep)
Species & Habitats		
Species distribution models	Link to the specific MPA Europe map platform tab	MPA Europe (OBIS, 2024: Principe et al., submitted)
Habitat-forming species distribution models	Link to the specific MPA Europe map platform tab	MPA Europe (OBIS, 2024: Principe et al., submitted)
Biogenic habitat distribution models	Link to the specific MPA Europe map platform tab	MPA Europe (OBIS, 2024: Principe et al., submitted)
EUSeaMap (2023) habitat types	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution – converted from shapefile.	EMODnet SH
Blue Carbon		
OC in marine sediments (EURO-CARBON)	Shape file with sampling points (.gpkg format)	MPA Europe (Graversen et al., 2025; Lønborg et al., 2025)
OC in marine sediments (model)	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original.	MPA Europe (Lønborg et al., submitted)
Physical Environmental		
Bathymetry*	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original.	MPA Europe (Assis et al., 2023) + Bio-ORACLE (Assis et al., 2018, 2024)
Terrain ruggedness, topographic heterogeneity, or rugosity	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution – reprojected	MPA Europe (this study, Harris et al., 2014)
Seafloor geomorphic features	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original	MPA Europe (Assis et al., 2023) + Bio-ORACLE (Assis et al., 2018, 2024)
Seabed slope		

Layer	Metadata	Main Source
Wave fetch (wave exposure)*	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original.	MPA Europe (Burrows et al., 2023)
Current speed*	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original.	MPA Europe (Assis et al., 2023) + Bio-ORACLE (Assis et al., 2018, 2024)
River runoff	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution – reprojected.	MPA Europe (this study; HydroSHEDS)
Distance to coast*	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original.	MPA Europe (Assis et al., 2023) + Bio-ORACLE (Assis et al., 2018, 2024)
<i>Temperature and Chemical Environmental</i>		
Sea surface temperature*		
Sea bottom temperature*		
Air temperature*		
Salinity*		
pH		
Oxygen concentration*		
Sea ice cover*	Cloud-optimized raster file (GeoTIFF) at 0.05 resolution - original.	MPA Europe (Assis et al., 2023) + Bio-ORACLE (Assis et al., 2018, 2024)
Phytoplankton concentration		
Mixed layer depth		
Nitrate concentration*		
Phosphate concentration		
Diffuse attenuation coefficient		
Photosynthetically available radiation*		

Figure 1. Screenshots of the [MPA Europe atlas on the OBIS platform](https://shiny.obis.org/distmaps/). Users can select species of interest and overlay them with the RBA and environmental layers. Species can be shown as their reported observations, predicted range at present and projected range under five climate change scenarios by 2050 and 2100. Of the 12,000 species included, about 900 are human-introduced species.

